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Challenges in the transition from School to career in Germany: Teachers as career choice mentors?

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Abstract

Vocational orientation is a task that is part of the educational mission of general education schools in Germany. The implementation of this task continues to prove difficult. There are various reasons for that. For example, the cross-sectional task has yet to be anchored in many federal states in the curriculum. Also, many teachers face this task sceptical, partly because they do not understand its scope and significance yet and partly because they do not feel prepared sufficiently for it. This article takes up a research desideratum in which the teachers' perspective on the school field of "Vocational Orientation" (VO) is represented. Subjective assumptions and theories of teachers regarding this area of action are considered. Additionally, besides a positioning in the scientific discourse, the results of a qualitative interview study will be shown.

Keywords

career choice decision; career and higher education guidance; career guidance teachers; beliefs of teachers

1. Introduction

Embarking on vocational training or higher education is usually preceded by a long process of choosing a career in which the individual balances his or her personal interests, aptitudes, talents, values (which are generally determined by his or her family) and plans for life against the requirements and demands of the world of work (Bußhoff 1992). In the light of high dropout levels from vocational training and higher education and a high number of young people in what is known as the "transition system" [between school and vocational training], demands for general-education schools to support and mentor young people in the career choice process have been being raised in Germany for years.

Vocational orientation has been more or less explicitly anchored as a task of school in the school laws of the individual federal states. This task has been concretised in administrative regulations and decrees specific to them, but in many places there is still no binding curricular anchoring of this cross-sectional task.

The theoretical and/or empirical concepts for the design and implementation of school-based vocational and study orientation that have emerged in recent years from career choice and career orientation research (cf. Butz 2008; Schudy 2008; Driesel-Lange et al. 2011; Kayser 2013) have not been taken up by education policy yet. Only a few federal states have created binding standards with regard to the objectives and contents of "vocational orientation" for years 5-10 and 7-12.

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A recent recommendation by Germany's Standing Conference of Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs proposes that, regardless of school type and the type of programme being pursued, careers education should be part of the curriculum at ISCED levels 2 and 3 in every school (KMK 2017).

2. Teachers as Career Mentors?

In academic discourse, teachers are ascribed a central role in the implementation and the design of school-based vocational and study orientation (Kayser 2013, p. 9; Dreer 2013, p. 150 ff.; Nentwig 2018, p. 79 ff.). On the one hand they have direct contact with young people because of their work. They experience and accompany them over many teaching hours, months and years. There also exist (more or less intensive) contacts to the parental homes. On the other hand, teachers are the "Makers" (Dreer, Driesel-Lange & Schindler 2011, p. 7) of school and vocational orientation, i. e. they shape school and teaching primarily responsibly and independently. That means: If teachers are aware of the task of "vocational orientation" and also pursue it, they can set appropriate priorities. Ideally, teachers - in the course of imparting specialist knowledge and technical skills - continuously encourage pupils to think about themselves and their life plans and to deal with topics that are relevant for life after school (cf. Deeken & Butz 2010). Furthermore, they provide insights into the world of work and occupation within the framework of a wide variety of vocational and study orientation measures, and provide impetus for individual school career planning and for the selection of follow-up options¹.

Overall, little is known about which attitudes teachers have with regard to the task of designing and implementing school-based vocational and study orientation or which beliefs they have concerning this matter.

3. Beliefs of Teachers in the Area of Action of "Vocational Orientation"

Teachers act on the basis of a complex structure of convictions, values and motivations on the one hand and knowledge and skills on the other (cf. Nentwig 2018, pp. 120 & 133). The latter are the result of a multitude of formal, non-formal and informal educational processes. Beliefs are complex, quite permanent, mental structures that comprise a person's knowledge of a specific object or domain and are stored in long-term memory. These structures incorporate findings from training and further education as well as individual everyday experiences in equal measure. Beliefs fulfil similar functions as scientific theories - they serve, for example, to explain certain facts or forecast developments. In contrast to scientific theories, they do neither necessarily exist explicitly and are not intersubjectively valid, nor are they subject to any quality criteria. They can be changed by experience (cf. Dann 1983, p. 80; Groeben, Wahl, Schlee & Scheele 1988, p. 17 ff.). It is of enormous importance that beliefs guide and control action. This means that teachers act in schools and lessons on the basis of more or less conscious beliefs.

The subjective theories teachers have about the school field of action of "vocational orientation" have so far hardly been investigated. Here, there is an obvious desideratum of re-

¹ "Kein Abschluss ohne Anschluss" [No degree without a connection] is a very popular statement which expresses that the school objective of leading pupils to a (good) school leaving certificate, which has often been the case up to now, falls short of the mark. Rather, it is a matter of sounding out individual connection options and pursuing them.

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search which - against the background of the importance of subjective theories for the implementation of the school task - is unsatisfactory.

The following remarks represent a first approximation to this field of research. The findings have been generated within the framework of the project *Selbsterkundung und Förderung individueller Entscheidungen (SELFIE)* [Encouraging Self-Exploration and Individual Decision-Making among Pupils]. Within the project duration (2017-2019), teaching materials for vocational orientation in grades 7, 8 and 9 for schools in Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (Germany) were and are being developed. In order to ensure the implementation and use of these materials, the accompanying research aims in particular at the current practice of school-based vocational and study orientation. In the first year of the project, qualitative, guided expert interviews were conducted with responsible teachers and school management. Figure 1 provides an overview of the focal points and structure of the scientific accompanying research. For this article, the data from the first interview survey (July 2017) are used.

Fig. 1 Overview of scientific accompanying research in the SELFIE project

At the beginning of the project, the focus of the accompanying research was on the question of how the practice of school-based vocational orientation presents itself at the schools participating in the project (n=12) and which framework conditions for the development and implementation of the SELFIE materials have to be considered. In this context, the beliefs of teachers regarding the design of school-based vocational orientation were also of interest.

Research questions were, for example:²

² Due to the limited scope of the text, only selected results can be presented in the context of this article. For a comprehensive assessment of the interview materials, please refer to the project documentation, which will be published at the end of 2019.

- What are the backgrounds of experience and knowledge on which teachers argue when they talk about the design of vocational orientation at their school?
- What objectives should school-based vocational orientation pursue from their point of view?
- What challenges and limits do they see in the design and implementation of vocational orientation?

In the summer of 2017, 12 qualitative, guided expert interviews were conducted with school principals and teachers. Figure 2 shows the interview survey in greater detail.

Fig. 2 Overview of the interview survey

The interviewed teachers are those we work within the SELFIE project, i.e. with whom we develop and test the SELFIE concept and the set of exercises. The teachers are employed at 12 schools spread across the federal state of Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania. Seven regional schools, three special schools, a grammar school and a school centre with grammar and regional school sections are represented. The interviewees differ regarding their functions and tasks at the respective schools. Among the respondents (n=18) there are six persons who belong to the school management. Eight teachers teach the subject of Arbeit-Wirtschaft-Technik [Work-Economy-Technology] and the same number are subject teachers for other disciplines. Ten of the persons state "vocational orientation" as an explicit additional task of their vocational activity. At the date of the survey 14 of these persons were members of the SELFIE work group, which is actively involved in the development and implementation of SELFIE.

3.1 Relevant Experience Backgrounds and Proficiency of Teachers for Vocational Orientation

Beliefs develop from different experiences and insights. So the question is: Which experiences do the teachers have for vocational-orientation work at school?

In the interviews, four persons explicitly refer to VO-related ranges of experience deriving from their own vocational training or professional practice preceding the teacher occupation. One person reported the completion of a teacher internship. Especially the insights into the world of work apart from school and university can be regarded as important resources for the realization of VO-activities.

The main reference for designing vocational orientation, however, is the interviewees' current school-based activity: They refer to the implementation of the framework curriculum for the subject Arbeit-Wirtschaft-Technik [Work-Economy-Technology], their activity as a VO-contact teacher, the preparation and follow-up of the students' internships, the organization and implementation of other VO-measures. In other words: The teachers apparently acquire their knowledge within the framework of their present tasks, thus "learning by doing". Regarding further education, the teachers, if at all, participated in specific VO-trainings or -offers (e.g. for the portfolio "Berufswahlpass" or the program "Lions-Quest"). Only one person received further training in the field of vocational orientation during their teacher training by attending a relevant certified course – albeit with premature exit. The teachers do not have any relevant and comprehensive education and training to prepare them for these activities. Nor do they mention the consultation of specialized literature or the like in the interviews. This does not necessarily mean that the teachers have not used these forms of gaining knowledge yet. It seems, however, that these forms of dealing with the subject were not perceived as sufficiently significant.

3.2. Objectives of School-Based Vocational Orientation

Teachers were asked to name the objectives that should underlie the design of school-based career guidance. It can be anticipated that the teachers do not explicitly refer to (current) findings in career choice or career orientation research, but rather carry out their individual thoughts and assumptions. The following objectives were named:

- To motivate pupils to deal with their own career choices,
- To foster the pupils' development of personality and to strengthen their self-concept,
- To enable pupils to make informed and realistic career choices, including plan B and plan C,
- To lead the pupils to a successful school-leaving certificate and to prepare the transition to the next stage of life.

This catalogue of objectives reflects essential goals and contents that are being discussed in the current discourse. However, a differentiated analysis shows that not all teachers have a comprehensive understanding of school-based vocational orientation work, but rather refer to individual aspects. A detailed presentation of the results is unfortunately not possible in this contribution due to the text limitation.

3.3. Challenges and Limits of School-Based Vocational Orientation

The original plan was to ask teachers about the concrete implementation of school-based vocational orientation, to record their expertise and to reconstruct the subjective theories underlying expert knowledge. However, the interviews revealed that the teachers used a compara-

tively high proportion of the interview time to identify the manifold, subjectively significant challenges and limits of school-based vocational orientation. This was initially a surprising finding for us: Instead of answers from practice, we received questions from practice. The following questions turned out to be particularly urgent:

- What do teachers need to know and be able to do? This question was posed by the teachers both with regard to the different contents of vocational orientation (knowledge of occupations, labour markets, etc.) and with regard to the heterogeneous body of pupils (support of pupils who lack communicative or social skills or pupils who are physically or psychologically impaired).
- What is the task of teachers in the career choice process, what are the tasks of other actors (career counsellors of the Federal Employment Agency, parents, school social workers, etc.)?
- How can cooperation with heterogeneous parental homes be successful?
- How can vocational orientation be integrated into school when there is no (additional) time for it?

In view of the extremely complex and demanding task of professionally accompanying young people in their choice of career, these questions are not surprising. However, it is clear that there is an enormous need for support and guidance on the teachers' part.

4. Summary and Outlook

The investigation and analysis of the subjective theories of teachers in the field of vocational orientation is an important field of research. The beliefs of the interviewed teachers prove to be variously complex and differentiated. While some teachers have an elaborated set of knowledge and can build up a nuanced argumentation on VO-specific questions, other teachers seem insecure. According to their own statements, they lack the knowledge and know-how to shape school-based vocational orientation. There is a clear need for special support, which must be met by education policy and the responsible Ministry of Education, among others.

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